

Deliverable D7 within 19ENG08

- Summary report describing the schedules for the three measurement campaigns to determine the efficiency of nacelles and their components on test benches with a target uncertainty of 1 % including pre-tests, measuring devices, and transfer standard specifications and their installation conditions -

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1 Introduction

In March 2022, the European Commission proposed a “joint European action for more affordable, secure and sustainable energy” [1]. To make Europe independent from Russian fossil fuels, main goals are to boost energy efficiency and increase renewables. Wind energy has much potential to speed up this green transition. For boosting the energy efficiency of wind turbines, a traceable and comparable efficiency determination method for nacelle drive trains and their components on nacelle test benches (NTBs) is required.

A new efficiency determination method for nacelles on NTBs based on traceable mechanical and electrical power measurement has been developed. This method needs to be tested and assessed on different nacelle and generator test benches using different devices under test (DUTs). To demonstrate the comparability of a traceable efficiency determination, measurement campaigns not only on different test benches but also on the same test bench using the same DUT with different drive train concepts are performed: full converter vs. double fed induction generator (DFIG).

This report was generated in Work Package 4 (WP4) of the EMPIR project 19ENG08 “Traceable mechanical and electrical power measurement for efficiency determination of wind turbines” short WindEFCY. The aim of this report is a detailed documentation of the thoroughly planned measuring campaigns at the 10 MW nacelle test bench (NTB) DyNaLab of Fraunhofer IWES (FhG) (section 4), at the 4 MW NTB at the Center for Wind Power Drives (CWD) of RWTH Aachen University (section 5), and at the generator test bench HiL-GridCoP of FhG (section 6) including the topology of the transfer standards. Moreover, it contains the efficiency determination method (section 2) including pre-tests, load sequences and the specification of the transfer standards for mechanical and electrical power measurement (section 3). This report is the base for all measurements within WP4 and therefore for the main output of the project.

2 Efficiency determination method

The efficiency of electrical machines can be determined either directly or indirectly. The direct efficiency determination is based on mechanical and electrical power, i.e., input and output power measurements. Whereas the indirect efficiency determination method uses electrical power and power losses measurements, i.e., summation of losses. IEC 60034-2-1 explains the test methods for the determination of losses and the efficiency classification. [2] [3]

2.1 State-of-the-art

Efficiency of electrical machines, η , is defined as the ratio of useful output, P_{out} , to total input, P_{in} :

$$\eta = \frac{P_{out}}{P_{in}} \quad (1)$$

For DUTs on NTBs, the energy efficiency is determined by measuring the electrical output power, P_{elec} , which is the sum of the electrical power per phase, $P_{1...3}$, and the mechanical input power, P_{mech} , which is the product of torque, M , and rotational speed, n :

$$\eta = \frac{P_{out}}{P_{in}} = \frac{P_{elec}}{P_{mech}} = \frac{P_1 + P_2 + P_3}{M \cdot n \cdot \frac{2\pi}{60 \text{ s/min}}} \quad (2)$$

For all parameters SI units are used except for rotational speed n (Table 1). Since min^{-1} is commonly used for electrical machines instead of the SI unit rad/s , a converting factor $\frac{2\pi}{60 \text{ s/min}}$ is added in (2).

Table 1: Descriptions of the measurement parameters

Symbol	Unit	Description
$P_{1...3}$	W	Effective power of three phases
P_{elec}	W	Total electrical power
M	N·m	Torque input of the DUT
n	min^{-1} (SI unit rad/s)	Shaft rotational speed
P_{mech}	W	Shaft mechanical power
P_{out}	W	Mechanical input of the DUT
P_{in}	W	Electrical output of the DUT
η	%	Efficiency of the DUT

In the following, standards, a calorimetric method and so-called ISO-efficiency contours for the efficiency determination of rotating electrical machines are introduced.

2.1.1 Efficiency determination of rotating electrical machines

Standard methods for determining losses and efficiency of rotating electrical machines from tests are defined in IEC 60034-2-1 [2]. In IEC 60034-2-1 the tests are grouped into three main approaches: direct, indirect, and back-to-back power measurements. These measurements are the base for the efficiency determination.

For the direct method, both input and output power are measured directly on a single machine under test. This direct power measurement of the electrical input and the mechanical output needs to be very accurate. Due to the relatively large measurement uncertainty of the mechanical power measurement, mainly the torque measurement, the direct method is only recommended for induction machines with a rated power < 1 kW.

The indirect method is also called single loss procedure. The actual loss is comprised of certain losses in a machine. The dissipated mechanical power, P_{out} , is calculated as the difference of the sum of the separately determined losses from the consumed electrical power, P_{in} :

$$P_{out} = P_{in} - P_{Cu1} - P_{Fe} - P_{Rb} - P_{Cu2} - P_{LL} \quad (3)$$

where P_{Cu1} are coil copper, P_{Fe} iron (magnetisation and eddy current losses), P_{Rb} friction, P_{Cu2} rotor copper, and P_{LL} are residual losses. The residual losses are load-dependent and can be computed by

a mathematical function or by measurements at different load points in the range from 125 % to 25 % of the rated machine torque. This method is to be used for machines with a rated power > 1 kW.

To perform the back-to-back method, two identical machines need to be mechanically connected back-to-back. The advantage of this method is, that the measurement of the mechanical power, which is tainted with a relatively large measurement uncertainty, can be avoided.

2.1.2 Alternative back-to-back method for nacelles on test benches

The back-to-back efficiency determination method got extended by Zhang et al. [4] [5] for the efficiency determination of nacelles on test benches. For the efficiency determination, the DUT and the NTB are connected mechanically back-to-back and operated in two modes with opposite energy flow directions: (A) normal mode where the NTB acts as the motor and the DUT as the generator, and (B) reverse mode where the DUT is the motor and NTB is the generator.

For both modes the same DUT, the same NTB, the same measuring chains, the same rotational speed in opposite directions, and similar load cases and conditions evoked by the active controlling are used. As a reference for the two operating modes depending on the measurement scenario, either the torque load or the electrical power is taken (Figure 1). The torque is measured on the connecting shaft between the NTB and the DUT's generator, while the electrical power is measured between the DUT's generator and the power converter. In both modes, the temperature of the bearing and the generator must be similar.

Figure 1: Mean values of mechanical and electrical power in the two test modes (A) and (B) of the alternative back-to-back method by Zhang et al. Based on [5].

In normal mode (A), the mean values of mechanical, $P_{\text{mech.A}}$, and electrical power, $P_{\text{elec.A}}$, are used to calculate the efficiency η :

$$\eta = \frac{\bar{P}_{\text{elec.A}}}{\bar{P}_{\text{mech.A}}} = \frac{\bar{P}_{\text{elec.A}}}{\bar{P}_{\text{elec.A}} + \bar{P}_{\text{Loss.A}}} = \frac{\bar{P}_{\text{elec.A}}}{\bar{P}_{\text{elec.A}} + k_A \bar{P}_{\text{Loss.total}}} \quad (4)$$

where the proportionality factor k_A is the ratio of power losses in mode (A) and the total power losses, $P_{\text{Loss.total}}$. The electrical power is averaged in the time domain. Its averaging period is set by the averaging period of the mechanical power averaged in the angle domain.

The sum of the differences in the mechanical and electrical power in both modes (A) and (B) is the total power loss:

$$\bar{P}_{\text{Loss.total}} = \bar{P}_{\text{mech.A}} - \bar{P}_{\text{mech.B}} + \bar{P}_{\text{elec.B}} - \bar{P}_{\text{elec.A}} \quad (5)$$

Because of this, the total power loss uncertainty is only depending on the uncertainties of the mechanical and electrical power changes. An expanded uncertainty ($k = 2$) of less than 1 % for the determined efficiency at rated power can be achieved.

This method is rather time-consuming as all operation points have to be met twice. Another disadvantage is the temperature-dependence of some loss types, e.g., stator winding losses. Consequently, the temperature of the DUT should be as equal as possible in both power flow directions. Moreover, not all NTBs can be run in reverse mode.

One of the biggest advantages is that the method can be used for specimens of all sizes without having dramatical price increases or technical restrictions since no accurate mechanical measurement is needed. The only condition is that the electrical measurement systems are available on the market.

2.1.3 Calorimetric method for devices on test benches

The calorimetric method uses the advantage of accurate power loss measurements and quantifies the power losses, P_{loss} , in form of heat:

$$\eta = \frac{P_{\text{out}}}{P_{\text{in}}} = \frac{P_{\text{in}} - P_{\text{loss}}}{P_{\text{in}}} = 1 - \frac{P_{\text{loss}}}{P_{\text{in}}}. \quad (6)$$

Sources for the heat are mechanical friction, lubrication and losses in the electrical systems. Normally, the heat is emitted into the surroundings via conduction, convection and radiation. This heat can only be measured by constituting a new boundary including additional measurement equipment. In [6] the calorimetric method was used. An insulating housing was built around the DUT to minimise the thermal output into the environment. By installing a thermal barrier around the DUT, most of the heat is emitted through the DUT's active cooling system. In case of a thermal equilibrium inside the new boundary, the main heat loss is the same as the heat conducted by the active cooling system, $P_{\text{conv,water}}$. It can be calculated by the volumetric flow rate and the temperature difference between outlet and inlet. Further parts of the power loss are listed in [6]. For an efficiency calculation acc. to (6), the input power, P_{in} , is required, which consists of mechanical and electrical input power:

$$P_{\text{in}} = P_{\text{in,mech}} + P_{\text{in,elec}}. \quad (7)$$

Base for the mechanical input power, $P_{\text{in,mech}}$, are input torque and rotational speed which should ideally be traced to national standards. The electrical power on the other side, $P_{\text{in,elec}}$, can be taken from the data sheet of the electrical oil pump.

For a warm-up period optimised measurement approach, it is important to go from small to large input powers and waiting at each step until a thermal equilibrium is reached. At thermal equilibrium the measurands are averaged over several minutes. The two input parameters torque and rotational speed define the operation points.

This method is suitable for validating small improvements of efficiency close to 100 % efficiency because of its small errors below 0.5 %. To determine the efficiency of full-size multi-megawatt nacelles, this approach is not practical as it is very time-consuming to reach a stationary temperature at current operation point and housing a full-size nacelle is very challenging.

2.1.4 ISO-efficiency contours

ISO-efficiency contours, also called efficiency maps, were used to characterise the efficiency of a motor operated by variable speed drives in its full operating range in [7], [8] and [9]. Hereby, the efficiency values for each operating point are determined using the direct method: accurate measurement of mechanical output power and electrical input power; moreover, the supply voltage quality is monitored. Based on these measurements, the ISO-efficiency contours (Figure 2) are calculated. This approach is already used in the combustion motor technology and drive trains of electrical vehicles. The amount of measurement points must be a compromise between the accuracy of the ISO-efficiency contours and the measurement effort. As for the direct efficiency determination acc. to IEC 60034-2-1, the measurements are taken in a steady state, which means at constant speed and constant torque load. To reach a stable state, the motor needs to be operated at rated value. The allowed change in temperature during the measurements amounts to 5 K. It was found in [8], that there are higher efficiency gradients in the lower speed and torque area, which required more measurement points in this range. Due to this, the measurement points are not evenly distributed over the motor's operating range. [7, 8, 9]

Figure 2: Analytical ISO-efficiency contour example of an induction motor with 4 kW, 400 V, and a rated speed of 1500 min⁻¹ taken from [8].

2.2 Measurement procedure

Standardised measurement procedures such as IEC 60034-2-1 are not designed for nacelle test benches that operate at different wind speeds meaning at different rotational speeds. In [7], [8], and [9], so-called efficiency maps or ISO-efficiency contours were introduced. This method plots the efficiency values as function of speed and torque as abscissa and ordinate respectively [7]. It has been found to be particularly useful for characterisation and design of drive trains for electrical vehicles. In the case of wind turbines, the overall efficiency is influenced by many different factors: gearbox, generator, transformer, converter, filters, bearings, control algorithms, and the cooling system. In order to be able to find and determine the highest efficiency and thus the best possible interaction of all these components, it is suitable to transfer the concept of ISO-efficiency contours to the determination of the efficiency of nacelles in test benches. The method of loss segregation is not or only to a limited extent applicable due to the complexity of this approach for nacelles on test benches (see section 2.1.3).

2.2.1 Characterisation maps

In order to be able to calculate ISO-efficiency contours, a large number of operating points at different speeds and torques must be recorded. Here the arrangement of the operating points (Figure 3) is referred to as characterisation map (cm). The main approach is a cm composed of two different types of torque and rotational speed combinations and load sequences: for cm1 the torque M is held periodically constant, and the rotational speed n is accelerated and decelerated stepwise. Whilst for cm2 n is held constant and M is increased and decreased stepwise in order to analyse the influence of the rotational speed on the torque signal.

Before the measured values at an operating point are taken, stable working conditions must be ensured. Above all, the torque must not be recorded as a single value due to the type of measurement, the torque ripples and the possible additional influences caused by mounting misalignments along the drive train. In general, DAQ should be continuous. To determine the reproducibility, performing each cm type should be repeated three times.

In the field, wind turbines are speed controlled with torque feedback. The control mode to perform the efficiency determination should be selected accordingly. Moreover, for a first efficiency determination of the DUT, no additional loads created by the load application system should be applied.

The measurement points for all the measurands required to determine the efficiency of the DUT (M and n) are individually defined for the respective set-ups in the following chapters.

Figure 3: Characterisation maps to define the measurement points for the calibration procedure within the operating range of the NTB and the DUT.

If the measurements are aborted, with increasing (decreasing) torque / rot. speed, the measurements must be started at the previously lowest (highest) torque / rot. speed point. In case of negative torque (torque inversion) due to an emergency brake event, the measurement set-up should be pre-loaded with maximum torque and maximum rotational speed before resuming the calibration measurements. This is to eliminate mechanical remanence.

As the direct measurement method is used, accurate instrumentation is required. The mechanical input quantities torque and rotational speed and the electrical output quantities voltage, current and phase are to be measured.

2.2.2 (Static) zero signal determination

The zero of the torque signal (also called offset) is to be determined as an average over different rotational positions. In order to be able to test various averaging possibilities, as shown in Figure 4, the single signals in the following positions relative to the starting position are to be taken:

Ideally, the measurements are to be conducted before and after a warming up test of the mechanical components to investigate the temperature influence on the static zero signal determination.

The zero signal should be averaged over at least 3, 4, and 6 relative positions to get S_3 , S_4 , and S_6 which can be compared to each other and to the rotational zero signal to find the optimal zero signal that can be used to tare the measurement values of the characterisation maps in a post-processing.

Figure 4: Static zero signal determination.

2.2.3 Rotational zero signal determination

The rotational zero signal, as depicted in Figure 5, is the arithmetic mean over at least six revolutions at a minimum rotational speed n_{\min} . The DAQ is to be continuous. To be able to calculate several rotational zero signals, the measurement time should be no less than $t_{\min} = 1$ min. The arithmetic averaging must not include the starting and, thereby, breakaway torque.

Figure 5: Rotational zero signal determination.

For the rotational zero signal determination, the torque signal needs to be controlled to zero by operating the DUT as a motor. In doing so, friction and breakaway torque are compensated. If possible, the rotational zero torque condition could be tested also without any kind of closed-loop controller, just in order to register the output values of the involved sensors.

2.2.4 Additional measurements

A heat run is dedicated to defining the warming up time of all mechanical components at maximum rotational speed n_{\max} and at a maximum torque M_{\max} . To monitor the temperature influence on the torque signals, a permanent data recording is necessary. The measuring time for this test is at least $t_{\min} = 4$ h. This measurement is also supposed to be used to analyse the temperature influence on the efficiency.

At the beginning of each measurement campaign in an NTB, an additional measurement at maximum rotational speed and maximum torque should take place for at least $t_{\min} = 10$ min in order to be able to determine the type A error of the torque measurement under rotation. This is important because the DUT and its control can have an influence on the NTB's control and its torque measurement and thus on the stability of the operating points. This error is considered in the overall measurement uncertainty by the uncertainty of the torque signal per rotation.

2.3 Pre-tests

To determine the electrical output not only the root mean square (RMS) value and phase of current and voltage, but also the harmonics up to 25th order and the total harmonic distortion (THD) up to 40th order both on current and voltage are to be measured. Moreover, flicker on voltage needs to be recorded. It is of great importance that all measurands are recorded simultaneously with a single power analyser or with synchronised analysers and data recorders.

3 Transfer standards specifications

For traceable efficiency determination, transfer standards for mechanical and electrical power are developed in NMIs and prepared for the implementation in NTBs. The constructions and specifications of the transfer standards are described in this section.

3.1 Mechanical power transfer standard

The mechanical power transfer standard (MPTS) consists of a 5 MN m torque transfer standard (TTS) for torque measurement and an inclinometer for the measurement of rotational speed. The inclinometer is centred on the inner side of the TTS cover plate (Figure 6) so that the torque and rotational speed can be measured at the same position.

Figure 6: Transfer standard for mechanical power measurement consisting of a 5 MN m TTS and an inclinometer to calibrate mechanical power measurement in NTBs.

The TTS was calibrated at PTB on its 1.1 MN m torque reference machine and the relative measurement uncertainty ($k = 2$) in full range (5 MN m) is predicted to be $10.03 \cdot 10^{-4}$ using an extrapolation method [10]. Within the project, the TTS will be calibrated directly up to 5 MN m on the newly developed torque calibration machine at PTB's Competence Center for Wind (CCW).

The implemented inclinometer was statically calibrated at PTB and is proofed to have an angle measurement uncertainty of 0.01° . For rotating measurement condition, the additional influences of the shaft tilt angle (α), the mounting misalignment (β), the eccentricity (Δ) (Figure 7) are analysed in [11]. For rotational speed determination, the signal processing method and the measurement uncertainty of the time measurement are considered in [12]. Overall, the inclinometer can achieve 0.018 % relative measurement uncertainty at 4.5 min^{-1} .

Figure 7: Inclinometer integrated in the 5 MN m TTS [11].

3.2 Electrical power transfer standard

The reference power measurement system (RPMS) is used to calibrate the electrical power measurement system (EPMS) of the test benches on-site. It is set up of a commercial multi-channel power analyser, precision current transducers and high voltage dividers. The multi-channel power analyser LMG 671 (Figure 8, bottom) from ZES Zimmer is designed for a simultaneous and thereby synchronised measurement of narrow- and broadband values and harmonics and interharmonics up to 2000th order. At power frequency, the accuracy of the power measurement is $\pm(0.015\%$ of the measured value $+0.01\%$ of maximum peak value). [13]

The precision current transducers 2000 A (PCT2000/DL2000ID) from Danisense and ZES Zimmer are contact free, closed loop, flux gate based current measurement sensors. With a very good linearity ($\pm 0.0001\%$) and a full industrial temperature range, they are well suited for use as a transfer standard in NTBs. The accuracy specification for the amplitude and the phase varies with the frequency; from DC up to 10 Hz, the accuracy for the amplitude is $\pm 0.0007\%$ of the nominal input current root mean square (RMS). [14]

The precision wideband high voltage divider HST 12-3 (Figure 8, top left) from ZES Zimmer can measure up to 20 kV peak (16.8 kV RMS) with frequencies from DC up to 300 kHz. The divider ration is 4000 and the amplitude error amounts to $\pm 0.05\%$ (50 Hz) and a phase shift of $\pm 0.04^\circ$ (50 Hz). [15]

Figure 8: RPMS consisting of a commercial power analyser (bottom), a high voltage divider (top left), and precision current transducers (top right) to calibrate the electrical power measurement in NTBs.

4 Set-up at FhG IWES

The NTB at Fraunhofer IWES is called Dynamic Nacelle Testing Laboratory (DyNaLab, Figure 9). It is located in Bremerhaven, Germany. The NTB has a testing capacity of 10 MW featuring a nominal torque of 8.6 MN m. An overload up to 150 % is possible, which corresponds to 12.9 MN m. The hexapod, which normally applies non-torque loads, is switched off during the measurement campaign to spare the TTS from overload due to superimposed torque and bending moments. The deadweight of the hexapod is compensated by hydraulic cylinders to minimise the non-torque load on the TTS.

Figure 9: DyNaLab NTB with a capacity of 10 MW at Fraunhofer IWES in Bremerhaven, Germany. Modified based on [16].

4.1 Measurement set-up

The set-up of the DyNaLab NTB at FhG IWES is elaborated with an equivalent circuit diagram shown in Figure 10. On the left side, two drive motors are connected in series to generate the desired torque load on the low-speed shaft (LSS). Through the main bearing, integrated in the hexapod (NTL), the torque load is applied to the device under test (DUT) for electrical power generation. Due to the enormous power, the electrical power output of the DUT has two parallel connected three-phase systems with 630 V line-line voltage (secondary side). After the transformer, the voltage is up-scaled to the 20 kV line-line voltage medium-voltage grids (primary side).

4.2 Measuring points including required measuring devices

The MPTS is mounted as part of the LSS between the non-torque load unit (NTL) and the DUT. The mechanical power measurement of the NTB includes a torque adapter mounted right next to the MPTS and an encoder placed in the middle of the motors and the NTL. In this way, the MPTS is independent from the mechanical power measurement of the NTB as shown in Figure 10.

The electrical power is measured on both sides of the transformer in order to investigate the transformer behaviour. On the secondary side, an LMG power analyser of ZES Zimmer is implemented to measure the voltage through direct connection and the current through Rogowski coils. Another LMG power analyser is used to measure the electrical power on the primary side in the junction box. Here, three Danisense precision current transducers are installed for current measurement of the three phases. Due to technical restrictions, the primary voltage divider from section 3.2 cannot be installed. Therefore, the signals of the existing FhG voltage dividers are duplicated for usage. The FhG voltage dividers will be calibrated externally at PTB after the measurement campaign took place. More information about the electrical power supply equipment in the NTB can be found in [17].

Figure 10. Equivalent circuit diagram of the test set-up and overview of the measuring points including required measuring devices at FhG IWES.

4.3 Load sequences

Normally, the DUT limits the applicable loads. In this case, however, the TTS is the bottle neck as it is only loadable up to 5 MN m. All load points were checked for eigenfrequencies.

As explained before, cm1 is used to calibrate the torque measurement in the NTB at different rotational speeds. The number of torque and rotational speed steps is a compromise between the time required and as many calibration stages as possible. cm1a (Figure 11) is important to determine the hysteresis of the torque measurement to be calibrated and needs to be repeated at least three times ($m = 3$) to determine the reproducibility b . cm1b (Figure 12) is used to determine the repeatability b' at different rotational speeds without stopping the drive train; it is to be repeated at least once ($m = 1$).

Figure 11: cm1a load sequence to calibrate the torque measurement in the NTB with focus on reproducibility and hysteresis.

Figure 12: cm1b load sequence to calibrate the torque measurement in the NTB with focus on the repeatability.

To analyse the influence of rotational speed on the torque measurement, cm2 (Figure 13) is used. It is repeated twice ($m = 2$).

Figure 13. cm2 to analyse the influence of the rotational speed on the torque measurement in the NTB.

Moreover, several operation curves (ocs) to determine the efficiency of the DUT are performed as well as a heat run to analyse the influence of thermal effects. Two practical tests are carried out: the efficiency behaviour under different measures to reduce noise and the efficiency behaviour when parts of the generator are deactivated.

4.4 Topology of the transfer standards

For a smooth installation of the transfer and reference standards, the following topologies are used separately for the mechanical (subsection 4.4.1) and the electrical power measurement system (subsection 4.4.2). All measurements on the test bench side were synchronised via different protocols: PTPv2, NTP and IRIG-B.

4.4.1 Mechanical power measurement system

In Figure 14, the topology of the MPTS is presented for a clear overview. The TTS has eight channels in total for the measurement signals of torque and non-torque loads. For data recording, a data acquisition (DAQ) system consisting of three HBM QuantumX amplifiers is mounted inside the rotating shaft. The module MX840b is capable of communicating with the inclinometer via CAN bus and synchronising other modules to the external IRIG-B time synchronisation signal. Since the DAQ system rotates with the shaft during operation, the signal transmission and power supply are achieved through WLAN and slip rings.

During the preparation phase, one of the torque signals from the TTS was duplicated using the output function of MX430b and transmitted via the slip ring to the LMG power analyser. In addition, the rotational speed signal measured by the FhG encoder is split and fed to the power analyser as well, so that the efficiency can be online calculated in the power analyser. Due to the lack of accuracy because of multiple torque signal conversions, the efficiency is for observation purpose only and not for final calculation. After the test run, however, it was identified that a huge amount of noise is produced due to the signal splitting near to the transformer and frequency converters. Therefore, the additional measurement of mechanical power using the power analyser was not implemented.

Figure 14: Topology of the MPTS, its DAQ and telemetry system, and the synchronisation to the NTB's DAQ at FhG IWES.

4.4.2 Electrical power measurement system

In Figure 15, an overview of the RPMS installed in the DyNaLab test bench is given. In this specific set-up two LMG power analysers for the different measuring points F1 and F2 are deployed. At measuring point F1, currents are measured by Rogowski coils while voltages are tapped off using flat measuring probes and directly measured by the LMG. At measuring point F2, only current measurement is possible due to technical restrictions for the voltage divider of the RPMS. To overcome the missing measurand, the signals of the existing FhG voltage dividers are duplicated and feed into the LMG. For a full traceability of all measurands, the voltage measurement chain, consisting of a FhG voltage divider, a transmitter and a receiver, will be calibrated externally at PTB after completion of the measurement

campaign. The current of all three phases is gathered using the three Danisense current sensors of the RPMS. For an online efficiency calculation by the LMG software, both the torque and the rotational speed signal is required; the torque signal comes from the mechanical transfer standard while the rotational speed is measured by a test bench encoder and fed into a specially designed interface adapter for the LMG. All the data are recorded by a special programme created with LabView.

The LMGs are synchronised amongst each other. A synchronisation to the test bench DAQ, as planned, is, however, not possible due to the lack of a synchronisation function in the chosen commercial power analyser. In the post-processing a data synchronisation via significant peaks and cross-correlation can be performed to solve the issue.

Figure 15: Topology of the RPMS to calibrate the electrical power measurement in the NTB at FhG IWES.

4.5 Measuring schedule

In the following, the detailed measuring schedule for the measurement campaign at FhG IWES in the period from 06/12/2021 until 12/01/2022 is listed.

time	day				
	06/12/2021	07/12/2021	08/12/2021	09/12/2021	10/12/2021
09:00	Arrival	assembly	assembly	commissioning	commissioning
09:30					
10:00					
10:30					
11:00					
11:30					
12:00					
12:30					
13:00					
13:30	Assembly				
14:00					
14:30					
15:00					
15:30					
16:00					
16:30					
17:00					

time	day				
	13/12/2021	14/12/2021	15/12/2021	16/12/2021	17/12/2021
09:00	electronics warm up & NTB boot				
09:30	static zero signal c	static zero signal c	oc3 cold	oc4 cold	heat up
10:00	oc1 cold	oc2 cold			
10:30	cm1a-1 c	cm1a-2 c	cm1a-3 c	cm1b-1 c	
11:00					
11:30					
12:00					
12:30					
13:00					
13:30			oc3 warm	oc4 warm	no load run
14:00					
14:30	oc1 warm	static zero signal w	manual profile		
15:00					
15:30	slack time	slack time	cm2-1 w		
16:00					
16:30					
17:00	slack time	slack time	slack time		

		day				
time	03/01/2022	04/01/2022	05/01/2022	06/01/2022	07/01/2022	
09:00	electronics warm up & NTB boot					
09:30	oc6 cold	static zero signal c	oc8 cold	oc9 cold	manual test	
10:00		oc7 cold				
10:30	cm1a-4 c	cm2-2 c	cm1b-2 c	cm1-5 c		
11:00						
11:30						
12:00						
12:30						
13:00						
13:30						
14:00						
14:30						
15:00						
15:30	oc6 warm	oc7 warm	oc8 warm	oc10 warm		
16:00						
16:30						
17:00						static zero signal w

		day				
time	10/01/2022	11/01/2022	12/01/2022	13/01/2022	14/01/2022	
09:00	electronics warm up & NTB boot	electronics warm up & NTB boot	disassembly			
09:30	oc9 cold	warm up test				
10:00						
10:30						
11:00	oc11 cold					
11:30	influence of noise reduction measures on the efficiency					static zero signal c
12:00						
12:30						
13:00						
13:30						
14:00						
14:30						
15:00						
15:30						
16:00						
16:30	short cut test					
17:00						static zero signal w

5 Set-up at RWTH Aachen

At the Center for Wind Power Drives (CWD) of RWTH Aachen University in Aachen, Germany, on-shore wind turbines and their components with a rated power up to $P_{nom} = 4$ MW can be tested. The NTB (Figure 16) is operated by a low-speed synchronous prime mover that is directly coupled with the rotor hub flange of the DUT. To measure the torque, a designated torque transducer with a nominal torque of $M_{nom} = 2.7$ MN m ($M_{max} = 3.4$ MN m) is installed on the LSS between the prime mover and the NTL unit.

Figure 16: NTB at CWD of RWTH University including FVA nacelle. Modified based on [18].

5.1 Measurement set-up

In Figure 17 and Figure 18, the NTB measuring set-up including all designated measuring points at RWTH is represented in form of an equivalent circuit diagram. During the measurement campaign, the DUT is a special research nacelle with a rated power of $P_{nom} = 2.75$ MW ($M_{max} = 1.5$ MN m) owned by Forschungsvereinigung Antriebstechnik e. V. (FVA) [19] [20]. Originally, it is a full converter system with a main gearbox ($i = 63$) that translates the LSS mechanical input into high-speed mechanical input (HSS) suitable for the short-circuit asynchronous generator. To assess the efficiency of different drive train concepts using the newly developed efficiency determination method, the full converter is replaced by a double fed induction generator (DFIG) and the same measurements are repeated. For the torque calibration, the TTS is installed directly at the rotor hub flange of the DUT to measure the mechanical input power of the nacelle in the right place. The power output of the generator is 690 V line-line voltage on the secondary side, which is up-scaled by the transformer to 10 kV line-line voltage on the primary side.

*Currents and Voltages are effective values of the 3 phase system

Figure 17: Equivalent circuit diagram of the test set-up with full converter (2.75 MW FVA nacelle) at RWTH Aachen.

At the beginning of each measurement campaign, the NTB including the DUT must be put into operation, what is called commissioning. The functionality of the NTB and all measuring and data recording devices are checked and possible eigenfrequencies are searched for in the event of mechanical changes to the drive train. This is part of daily work for NTB operators.

*Currents and Voltages are effective values of the 3 phase system

Figure 18: Equivalent circuit diagram of the test set-up with DFIG at RWTH Aachen.

5.2 Measuring points including required measuring devices

As illustrated in Figure 19, the MPTS is mounted on the LSS directly at the DUT's rotor hub, which is between the NTL and the DUT, using specially designed adapters. In the NTB itself, the mechanical input power is measured by a torque transducer which is permanently installed in the drive train: between the motor and the NTL.

In case of the full converter concept, the electrical output power is measured in three points (Figure 19): between the generator and the power converter (F1), between the AC filter and the transformer (F2a), and between the transformer and the 10 kV grid (F3). At measuring point F1, the current of all three phases is measured by three ZES Danisense precision current transducers with 3000 A peak. At measuring point F2a, all six lines per phase need to be packaged together in order to measure the current using three ZES Danisense precision current transducers with 3000 A peak. At both points, the voltage is measured through direct connection with the LMG power analyser from section 3.2. Parallel to the LMG power analyser, a WT5000 power analyser is deployed as this can be synchronised to the NTB via PTPv2. On the primary side, at measuring point F3, three ZES Danisense precision current transducers with 3000 A peak are installed to measure the current. The voltage is measured by the high voltage divider ZES HST 12-3 with 3 inputs as described in section 3.2. All signals are fed into a second LMG power analyser that is synchronised to the first one.

Figure 19: Overview of measuring points including required measuring devices for test set-up F (for full converter) at RWTH Aachen.

Using the DFIG, the electrical power is measured in four points: same as for the full converter concept, current and voltage are measured between the transformer and the grid (D3 = F3) and at the point of common coupling, where the power lines coming from the generator’s rotor and its stator are being combined, which is between the AC filter and the transformer (D2b = F2a). The signals from measuring points D2b and D3 are gathered by a first LMG power analyser. In addition to the measuring points as for the full converter concept, current and voltage are measured by six ZES Danisense precision current transducers with 3000 A peak and directly via a second LMG power analyser between the generator’s stator and the converter (D1) and between the generator’s rotor and the converter (D2a). Again, parallel to this LMG power analyser, a WT5000 power analyser is deployed at D2a that is synchronised to the NTB via PTPv2.

As the mechanical power measurement in the NTB is to be calibrated during the first measurement campaign using the full converter DUT, further installation of the MPTS is not necessary.

Figure 20: Overview of measuring points including required measuring devices for test set-up D (for DFIG) at RWTH Aachen.

5.3 Load sequences

As the DUT limits the applicable torque load, the maximum torque is $M_{\max} = 1.5 \text{ MN m}$. The lower and upper boundaries for rotational speed are 12.5 min^{-1} and 17.5 min^{-1} respectively. All load points were checked for eigenfrequencies.

As cm1a (Figure 21) is used to calibrate the torque measurement in the NTB at different rotational speeds and to determine its hysteresis, this load sequence is repeated at least three times ($m = 3$). Cm1b (Figure 22) is used to determine the repeatability of the torque measurement. This load sequence is to be repeated at least once ($m = 1$).

Figure 21: cm1a load sequence to calibrate the torque measurement in the NTB with focus on reproducibility and hysteresis.

Figure 22: cm1b load sequence to calibrate the torque measurement in the NTB with focus on the repeatability.

To analyse the influence of rotational speed on the torque measurement, cm2 (Figure 23) is used. It is repeated twice ($m = 2$).

Figure 23: cm2 to analyse the influence of the rotational speed on the torque measurement in the NTB.

To characterise the efficiency of the DUT, the ISO-map, with measuring points in the peripheral areas of the operation range, extends the cms. This enables the creation of an efficiency characterisation map (Figure 24) with measuring points distributed over the entire working range of the DUT.

Figure 24: ISO-map to determine the DUT’s efficiency for its entire operation range.

For all cms and maps, the measuring time per load step should be at least $t_{\text{meas.min}} = 1$ min after the signal stabilisation in order to be able to average over six full revolutions.

5.4 Topology of the transfer standards

For a smooth installation of the transfer and reference standards, the following topologies are used separately for the mechanical (subsection 5.4.1) and the electrical power measurement system (subsection 5.4.2). All measurements on the test bench side were synchronised via different protocols: PTPv2 and NTP.

5.4.1 Mechanical power measurement system

The topology of the MPTS is depicted in Figure 25. In this set-up, the three HBM QuantumX amplifiers building the DAQ system are mounted around the flanges of the TTS on special platforms. The very precise 225 Hz carrier frequency amplifier MX238 is used to measure the torque signal. Again, module

MC840b is used to communicate with the inclinometer via CAN bus. Because of the rotation of the TTS including its DAQ system, power supply is provided via a slip ring. The telemetry system consists of a switch collecting all the data and two access points communicating via WLAN and transmitting the data for an in time overload surveillance to a laptop where the data is recorded.

Figure 25: Topology of the MPTS, its DAQ and telemetry system, and the synchronisation to the NTB's DAQ via NTP / PTP at RWTH Aachen.

5.4.2 Electrical power measurement system

The RPMS as installed in the NTB at CWD is given in Figure 26. Here, two LMG power analysers are deployed: one for measuring points F1 and F2a (full converter, DFIG: D1 and D2a) and the other one for measuring point F3 (full converter, DFIG: D2b and D3). At measuring points F1 and F2a (DFIG: D1, D2a and D2b), currents are measured by three Danisense current sensors each. The challenge here is that each phase consists of six individual lines that have to be combined for the measurement. Voltages in these places are tapped of using flat measuring probes and measured directly by an LMG power analyser. At measuring point F3 (DFIG: D3), the current of all three phases is gathered using three more Danisense current sensors of the RPMS while voltage is measured via the voltage divider of the RPMS.

The WT5000 power analyser is synchronised with the NTP server of the NTB. Since the LMG power analysers are only able to synchronise amongst each other, a rectangular pulse signal is fed into the WT5000 and the LMG power analysers simultaneously. Using the signal as a reference, the synchronisation between WT5000 and LMG power analysers can be established in a post-processing.

Figure 26: Topology of the RPMS to calibrate the electrical power measurement in the NTB at RWTH Aachen.

5.5 Measuring schedule

In the following, the detailed measuring schedules for the two measurement campaigns at RWTH Aachen are listed. The first measurement campaign using the full converter takes place from 25/07/2022 until 19/08/2022 while the second one using the DFIG is scheduled from 05/12/2022 until 16/12/2022.

Full converter concept measuring campaign

	day				
time	25/07/2022	26/07/2022	27/07/2022	28/07/2022	29/07/2022
08:00	assembly torque transfer standard				
08:30					
09:00					
09:30					
10:00					
10:30					
11:00					
11:30					
12:00					
12:30					
13:00					
13:30					
14:00					
14:30					
15:00					
15:30					
16:00					
16:30					

	day				
time	01/08/2022	02/08/2022	03/08/2022	04/08/2022	05/08/2022
08:00	assembly measurement technique	assembly measurement technique	commissioning	electronics warm up & NTB boot	electronics warm up & NTB boot
08:30				static zero signal c	cm1a-3 c
09:00				rotational zero signal cold	
09:30				cm1a-1 cold	
10:00					rotational zero signal warm
10:30				slack time	cm1b-1 w (alternatively on Monday)
11:00					
11:30				cm1a-2 warm	slack time
12:00					
12:30				slack time	slack time
13:00					
13:30				shut down	shut down
14:00					
14:30				shut down	shut down
15:00					
15:30				shut down	shut down
16:00	shut down				
16:30	shut down	shut down			
17:00			shut down		
18:00	shut down	shut down			
19:00			shut down		

	day					
time	08/08/2022	09/08/2022	10/08/2022	11/08/2022	12/08/2022	
08:00	electronics warm up & NTB boot	electronics warm up & NTB boot				
08:30						
09:00	slack time	static zero signal c	cm1b-2 c	heat run @ 1550 kN m and 17.5 min ⁻¹	reverse zero signal c	
09:30		cm1a-4 c			slack time	ISOv2-2 c
10:00						
10:30						
11:00						
11:30						
12:00	rotational zero signal c	static zero signal w	cm2-2 w	ISOv2-1 w	slack time	
12:30	slack time					
13:00		cm2-1 w				
13:30	cm1a-5 w					
14:00		reverse zero signal w				
14:30						
15:00	rotational zero signal w	slack time	slack time	slack time		
15:30						
16:00	slack time	slack time	slack time	slack time	slack time	
16:30						
17:00						
18:00	shut down	shut down	shut down	shut down	shut down	
19:00						

	day				
time	15/08/2022	16/08/2022	17/08/2022	18/08/2022	19/08/2022
08:00	electronics warm up & NTB boot	electronics warm up & NTB boot	slack time	disassembly measurement technique	disassembly measurement technique
08:30					
09:00	slack time	multi-component tests			
09:30					
10:00					
10:30					
11:00					
11:30					
12:00	multi-component tests				
12:30					
13:00					
13:30					
14:00					
14:30					
15:00					
15:30					
16:00	slack time	slack time			
16:30					
17:00					
18:00	shut down	shut down			
19:00					

DFIG concept measuring campaign

	day				
time	05/12/2022	06/12/2022	07/12/2022	08/12/2022	09/12/2022
08:00	electronics warm up & NTB boot	electronics warm up & NTB boot			
08:30					
09:00	assembly measurement technique	assembly measurement technique	commissioning	heat run @ 1550 kN m and 17.5 rpm	static zero signal c
09:30					rotational zero signal cold
10:00					cm1a-1 cold
10:30					
11:00					
11:30				ISOv2-1 w	
12:00					static zero signal w
12:30					rotational zero signal warm
13:00					slack time
13:30					
14:00					
14:30				shut down	
15:00					
15:30					
16:00				shut down	
16:30					
17:00					
18:00					
19:00					

	day						
time	12/12/2022	13/12/2022	14/12/2022	15/12/2022	16/12/2022		
08:00	electronics warm up & NTB boot	electronics warm up & NTB boot					
08:30							
09:00	slack time	cm1b-1 c	ISOv2-2 c	disassembly measurement technique	disassembly measurement technique		
09:30							
10:00							
10:30							
11:00							
11:30							
12:00	rotational zero signal c	slack time					
12:30		reverse zero signal w					
13:00	cm2-1 c	multi-component tests	multi-component tests				
13:30						slack time	
14:00							
14:30							
15:00							
15:30	rotational zero signal w						
16:00							
16:30	slack time	slack time	slack time				
17:00							
18:00	shut down	shut down	shut down				
19:00							

6 Generator test bench (HiL-GridCoP)

The HiL-GridCoP test bench at FhG IWES is implemented for high-speed generator and converter systems. It has a 9 MW drive with 13 MW overload capability. In this test bench, the high speed shaft (HSS) of the nacelle system is tested using the Hardware-in-the-Loop (HiL) method. Meanwhile, the test bench can reproduce different grid states using the grid simulator [21]. The allowed load application limits for the test bench generator configuration used are illustrated in Figure 27.

Figure 27: Maximum load application of torque and rotational speed for the DUT (generator) on the HiL-GridCoP test bench.

6.1 Load sequences

Based on the application limits of the test bench, two load sequences are developed for the measurements. Load sequence cm-A (Figure 28) is designed to analyse the influence of continuous load change (increasing and decreasing stepwise) of rotational speed on the torque measurement. This load sequence is to be repeated at least four times ($m = 4$).

Figure 28: Load sequence to analyse the influence of continuous load change of rotational speed on the torque measurement in the HiL-GridCoP test bench.

Load sequence cm-B (Figure 29) is designed to analyse the influence of fast changing rotational speed on the torque measurement. Cm-B should be repeated at least four times ($m = 4$). It is expected that

there will be a minimal change in torque measurement with speed due to additional forces and moments causing crosstalk on the torque measuring bridge. In addition, the accuracy of the DC control of the generator could be observed as a further effect on the torque measurement.

Figure 29: Load sequence to analyse the influence of fast changing rotational speed on the torque measurement in the HiL-GridCoP test bench.

For both cms, the measuring time per load step should be at least $t_{\text{meas.min}} = 4 - 8$ s after the signal stabilisation in order to be able to form an average value corresponding to a 0.2 Hz Bessel filter used for static calibration.

6.2 Topology, measuring points and required measuring devices

The topology diagram of the HiL-GridCoP test bench is presented in Figure 30. Outside the control room (CR), the drive motor is placed on the left side of the test bench and provides the required torque load for the generator (DUT). In between, torque is measured by the HBK T40FH transducer from FhG IWES and rotational speed is measured by an encoder. The generated electrical power is converted from low voltage (LV) side to the medium voltage (MV) side by a transformer and connected to the MV grid in the junction box (JB).

As there is no suitable TTS available from NMIs in this measurement range, the T40FH transducer is directly used and will be calibrated statically at PTB after the measurement campaign to provide traceability. The rotational speed is measured by a test bench internal encoder. The signals are fed to the WT5000 power analyser for an efficiency determination. In addition, a vibrometer from PTB is installed to measure the dynamic effects of the rotational speed.

For the electrical power measurement and the calibration, the RPMS provided by NMIs are installed alongside the FhG IWES measurement in the test bench (Figure 30). The first power analyser LMG 671 has six measurement channels to measure the LV and MV electrical power simultaneously with a harmonic analysis and a power quality evaluation. The second power analyser WT5000 measures the electrical power only on the MV side. It measures the torque signal from the T40FH and the rotational speed signal from the vibrometer synchronously and calculates the efficiency. In addition, the WT5000 can be synchronised with the test bench measurement through a PTPv2 signal. This enables the comparison between the RPMS and the FhG IWES measurement system in a post-processing.

Figure 30: Topology diagram of HiL-GridCoP test bench and the RPMS to calibrate the electrical power measurement.

6.3 Measuring schedule

In the following, the detailed measuring schedule for the measurement campaign at the HiL-GridCoP test bench of FhG IWES in the period from 17/03/2022 until 22/03/2022 are listed.

time	day				
	17/03/2022	18/03/2022	21/03/2022	22/03/2022	
07:30	Journey PTB colleagues	commissioning and measurement system check	electronics warm up & NTB boot	electronics warm up & NTB boot	
08:00			static zero signal	static zero signal	
08:30			cm-A	heat run	
09:00			cm-B		
09:30			heat run		heat run
10:00					
10:30					
11:00					
11:30	set-up vibrometer and reference power measurement system		heat run	cm-A	
12:00				cm-B	
12:30		cm-A			
13:00		cm-B			
13:30		static zero signal			
14:00		disassembly		cm-A	
14:30	cm-B				
15:00	cm-A				
15:30	Journey back to PTB	cm-B			
16:00		cm-A			
16:30	slack time	slack time	slack time		
17:00					

The torque transducer T40FH will be calibrated statically using PTB's 1.1 MN m torque standard machine after the measuring campaign at HiL-GridCoP.

7 Conclusion and future work

So far, there are no internationally accepted methods or standards for the efficiency determination of DUTs on test benches. Currently existing method to determine the efficiency of electrical machines, such as standards for the efficiency determination of rotating electrical machines, an alternative back-to-back method, a calorimetric efficiency determination method and ISO-efficiency contours were investigated and introduced in this report. A lack of non-aerodynamic, standardised, and easily reproducible efficiency determination methods was revealed. Based on this information, a new efficiency determination method for nacelles and their components on test benches was developed. This new method is based on calibrated mechanical and electrical power measurement. It was presented including individual pre-tests, zero signal determination and load cycles. The concept itself and the practicability of the measurement procedure will be evaluated throughout three extensive measurement campaigns in cooperation with industrial partners. To implement the measurements, the test benches were described with the necessary components and the measurement topology of the three different test benches including the dedicated measuring points and measuring devices were elaborated. Load cycles for the respective measurement campaigns were created based on the boundary conditions of the test bench and those of the test devices used as well as the possibilities of the reference measuring devices for the calibration of mechanical and electrical power measurement. In order to be able to use the available measurement time optimally, measurement schedules for all three test benches were drawn up.

This report is the base for all measurements within WP4 and therefore the main output of the project. The exemplary results of the efficiency determination from these measurement campaigns will be presented by the end of the project. This new method has promising potential to indicate the most desirable operation range of the test device and to determine the efficiency traceably.

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II Acronyms

cm	characterisation map
CR	control room
CWD	Center for Wind Power Drives
DAQ	data acquisition
DFIG	doubly fed induction generator
DUT	device under test
DyNaLab	dynamic nacelle testing laboratory
EMPIR	European Metrology Programme for Innovation and Research
EPMS	electrical power measurement system
EU	European Union
FhG IWES	Fraunhofer Gesellschaft - Institut für Windenergiesysteme
FVA	Forschungsvereinigung Antriebstechnik e. V.
HiL	Hardware-in-the-Loop
HSS	high-speed shaft
IRIG-B	inter range instrumentation group timecode B
JB	junction box
LAS	load application system
LSS	low-speed shaft
LV	low voltage
MPTS	mechanical power transfer standard
MV	medium voltage
NTB	nacelle system test bench
NTL	non-torque loading
NTP	network time protocol
PTB	Physikalisch-Technische Bundesanstalt
PTP	precision time protocol
PWM	pulse-width modulation
RMS	root mean square
RPMS	reference power measurement system
RWTH	Rheinisch-Westfälische Technische Hochschule Aachen
THD	total harmonic distortion
VTT	Technical Research Centre of Finland Ltd.
WindEFCY	Wind efficiency

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